

From Shock to Strategy: Quality of Life Indicators as Foundations for Post-Disaster Recovery in Türkiye

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Abstract

This article investigates the post-disaster quality of life (QoL) among survivors of the February 6, 2023, Kahramanmaraş-centered earthquakes in Türkiye. Drawing on data from a cross-sectional household survey conducted in Adana, Adıyaman, Hatay, and Kahramanmaraş, the study analyzes survivors' access to essential services, protection, shelter, and information. Using a survivor-centered and sociologically grounded approach, the research highlights multidimensional vulnerabilities across gender, age, and legal status—particularly among displaced populations and refugees under temporary protection. The analysis is framed by the social quality perspective, integrating indicators of socio-economic security, social inclusion, and psychological well-being. Findings reveal persistent gaps in food security, mental health, safe housing, and information accessibility, with significant disparities by province. This study contributes to disaster sociology by offering empirical evidence to inform early recovery planning, protection-focused humanitarian response, and equitable public policy. It emphasizes the need for intersectional and context-specific strategies to support recovery in disaster-affected settings.

Keywords

Post-disaster recovery, Quality of life, Earthquake survivors, Social vulnerability, Humanitarian response, Türkiye

Introduction

Türkiye is located on the geologically active Anatolian Plate, a major tectonic region that has experienced recurrent and destructive seismic activity throughout recorded history. Since the early 20th century, at least 20 earthquakes with magnitudes above 7.0 have occurred within its borders, placing the country among those with the highest seismic vulnerability globally. Between 1900 and 2023, Türkiye recorded 269 major earthquakes resulting in significant human casualties and widespread economic damage. Among these, the 2023 Kahramanmaraş Earthquake, the 1939 Erzincan Earthquake, and the 1999 Marmara Earthquake (centered in Gölcük) rank as the most devastating in terms of human and infrastructural losses (AFAD, 2023; Boğaziçi University Kandilli Observatory, 2023).

On February 6, 2023, two major earthquakes—measuring 7.7 and 7.6 in magnitude—struck the Pazarcık and Elbistan districts of Kahramanmaraş, situated along the East Anatolian Fault, also known as the Dead Sea Fault system (AFAD, 2023; Boğaziçi University Kandilli Observatory, 2023). The seismic shockwaves extended across a broad corridor from Hatay to Elazığ, severely damaging settlements along a 550-kilometer stretch. Hatay,

Kahramanmaraş, and Adıyaman emerged as the provinces most severely affected. The disaster's impacts were compounded by a 6.4 magnitude aftershock on February 21, centered in Hatay's Defne district, which exacerbated the already extensive destruction. In total, more than 50,000 fatalities were reported—over 45,000 in Türkiye and more than 7,000 in Syria—alongside tens of thousands of injuries and critical infrastructure collapse, generating a large-scale humanitarian emergency.

High-magnitude natural hazards, particularly earthquakes, are known to disrupt the quality of life (QoL) of survivors by inducing sustained psychological trauma, socioeconomic dislocation, and emotional instability (Cutter et al., 2008; Norris et al., 2008; Ozdemir et al., 2015). One of the most detrimental experiences is forced displacement due to unsafe or destroyed housing, which often leads to deteriorating living standards, social dislocation, and disruption of daily routines and community ties. These conditions are closely associated with reductions in subjective well-being and satisfaction across multiple domains of life. In our study, we analyzed the current QoL status of earthquake-affected populations, focusing on two distinct groups: host community members and Syrians under temporary protection.

Seismic disasters typically result in large-scale physical destruction and human loss, alongside extensive disruption to key economic sectors such as energy, transportation, trade, and communications. However, their psychosocial consequences are equally significant. The psychological strain caused by bereavement, injury, and the breakdown of daily services significantly increases the protection risks for affected individuals, particularly in provinces with severe infrastructural damage. The emotional trauma is compounded by limited access to basic needs and public services. These circumstances often give rise to mental health challenges, including symptoms of Acute Stress Disorder (within the first month post-event) and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) thereafter. In many cases, survivors also experience what is termed “ambiguous loss”—the emotional burden of missing family members whose fates remain unknown—hindering the grieving process and contributing to prolonged psychological distress.

An expanding body of empirical literature has investigated the psychological and social outcomes of survivors in the aftermath of earthquakes. A growing body of research consistently highlights the influential role of factors such as age, gender, educational attainment, and socio-environmental context in determining individual resilience and patterns of mental health outcomes (Bonanno et al., 2015; Bıçakcı & Okumuş, 2023; Yelboğa, 2023). Recent longitudinal research has further explored how exposure to traumatic seismic events correlates with decreased QoL, particularly through the mediating effects of PTSD and other trauma-related disorders (Ozdemir et al., 2015; Ceyhan & Ceyhan, 2007). In geographies characterized by chronic seismic risk, promoting psychosocial well-being is essential for both humanitarian response and the long-term effectiveness of recovery interventions.

Quality of life (QoL) is a multidimensional concept that encompasses individuals' subjective evaluations of their well-being, including their physical health, emotional stability, and perceived social and material circumstances (WHOQOL Group, 1995; Billington, 1999; Aaronson et al., 1988). As measured by standardized tools, QoL incorporates components such as functional independence, mental health, social integration, and satisfaction with one's

environment. Closely linked to the notion of health-related quality of life (HRQoL), it captures both personal experiences and structural determinants that influence well-being (Dimenas et al., 1990; WHOQOL Group, 1998).

To better understand the lived experiences of earthquake survivors, this study presents findings on a range of well-being indicators, including mental health status, access to protection mechanisms, informational awareness, access to basic services, response to urgent needs, and satisfaction with living conditions. The research is based on a cross-sectional household survey conducted between April and May 2023 in four severely affected provinces—Adana, Adıyaman, Hatay, and Kahramanmaraş. Participants were randomly selected from both vulnerable host community members and refugee households targeted by the recovery project.

This study contributes to a growing body of literature examining post-disaster quality of life (QoL) through a multidimensional and survivor-centered lens. By situating our findings within the frameworks of the capabilities approach (Sen, 1999; Nussbaum, 2000), subjective wellbeing theory (Diener, 1984), and post-crisis vulnerability (Norris et al., 2008), we demonstrate how intersecting forms of deprivation—educational, economic, psychosocial, and institutional—undermine survivors' ability to recover in both functional and dignified ways.

1. Literature Review

The concept of social quality emerged in the late 20th century as both a normative and analytical tool for examining the enabling conditions under which individuals engage meaningfully in economic, social, and cultural life. Developed by the European Foundation on Social Quality (EFSQ), this framework was conceived as a response to the inadequacies of conventional welfare measures such as GDP or income-based poverty metrics, offering a broader, multidimensional lens through which societal well-being could be assessed (Walker & van der Maesen, 2004; Beck et al., 2012). Within the domain of sociological inquiry into well-being, two dominant methodological orientations can be identified. The first, rooted in positivist epistemology, emphasizes the measurement of structural indicators—such as income levels, unemployment rates, health disparities, and environmental conditions—that shape individuals' life chances and reproduce social inequality. This approach aligns with macro-structural analyses and the legacy of functionalist thought.

By contrast, the second approach is informed by interpretivist methodologies that prioritize subjective well-being. It emphasizes self-reported assessments, capturing individuals' perceived quality of life based on their experiences, expectations, and the meanings they attach to social life. While both paradigms contribute valuable insights, scholars have long debated the conceptual and methodological tensions between them. Research has consistently shown that objective material conditions and subjective evaluations do not always correlate neatly, illustrating the complexity involved in operationalizing the notion of quality of life in empirical sociological studies.

Social quality is typically defined as the degree to which individuals are able to participate in societal life in a manner that enhances their dignity, well-being, and capacity for self-realization. It is organized around four interrelated domains: socio-economic security, social inclusion, social cohesion, and social empowerment (Walker & van der Maesen, 2004). Each domain represents a core dimension of social life: socio-economic security refers to stability in access to resources; social inclusion highlights participation in societal institutions and

networks; social cohesion points to the integrity of interpersonal and group relations; and social empowerment focuses on the individual's capacity to influence the course of their life and engage in collective decision-making processes.

A key strength of the social quality paradigm lies in its interdisciplinary orientation, which brings together insights from sociology, political science, economics, and cultural studies (Abbott & Wallace, 2012). This contrasts with models that privilege economic metrics alone, offering instead a more comprehensive approach that places human flourishing and active citizenship at the center of analysis. Operational efforts have attempted to translate these four domains into measurable indicators, combining both quantitative and qualitative methodologies (Beck et al., 2012). Empirical applications across the European Union have demonstrated the framework's value in uncovering regional inequalities, informing inclusive policy design, and promoting governance models responsive to diverse social needs (van der Maesen & Walker, 2012; Pehle & Herrmann, 2013; Abbott & Wallace, 2012). Furthermore, the conceptual flexibility of social quality has enabled its application to global issues such as forced migration, democratic erosion, and environmental precarity, reinforcing its relevance beyond its original European context (Pehle & Herrmann, 2013).

The concept of quality of life (QoL), which has gained significant prominence in both sociological and public health scholarship, represents an inherently multifactorial and context-sensitive construct. It encompasses a range of overlapping domains including physical health, mental and emotional well-being, social engagement, and subjective life satisfaction. This section aims to provide a conceptual and methodological overview of QoL, with particular attention to how it is operationalized in both sociological research and applied settings, including clinical and psychosocial interventions. The multidimensionality of QoL challenges overly reductive measurement strategies, such as standardized survey instruments, which may fail to capture the nuanced interplay between external constraints and personal perception.

To address this complexity, many QoL measurement tools incorporate both objective indicators—such as mobility limitations or access to services—and subjective assessments of contentment, autonomy, and future outlook. This dual focus highlights the necessity of integrating structural and experiential dimensions in well-being assessments. The World Health Organization (1998) defines quality of life as “an individual's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns.” This definition underscores two essential aspects: first, that QoL is fundamentally subjective and encompasses both positive and negative life domains; and second, that it is broad and multidimensional in scope.

In a similar vein, Hajiran (2006) conceptualizes social quality as the result of ongoing interactions between an individual's personality and the succession of life events they experience. These events unfold across multiple domains—ranging from liberty, education, and health to safety, spirituality, and social connection—each contributing uniquely to the individual's overall life experience.

Given its breadth, QoL must be understood not as a static state, but as a dynamic interplay between personal agency and structural opportunity. From a sociological standpoint, this calls for models that recognize the recursive and

interdependent nature of well-being's core dimensions. That is, the physical, psychological, and social elements of QoL do not operate in isolation, but influence each other in ways that are both context-specific and temporally variable. A comprehensive understanding of QoL thus demands a holistic analytical framework—one that can account for its fluid, relational, and life-course contingent character.

Over the past two decades, scholarly interest in post-disaster recovery has grown considerably, especially in response to large-scale catastrophes such as the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami, the 2010 Haiti earthquake, and the 2011 Tōhoku and Van earthquakes (Clinton, 2006; Aldrich, 2012; Benadusi, 2014; Tierney, 2014). These events have catalyzed a significant body of research examining the multifaceted challenges of reconstruction, psychosocial recovery, and resilience building in affected communities. Much of this research has centered on the psychological effects of disasters, with numerous studies assessing post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, and anxiety among survivors (Norris et al., 2002; Nakajima, 2012; Ozdemir et al., 2015). Complementing these psychological assessments, public health and development literature has focused on disruptions in housing, food security, and healthcare systems (Carr et al., 1997; Gowan et al., 2014).

However, these approaches often remain siloed—treating mental health, physical safety, and socio-economic needs as discrete domains—rather than examining how these elements intersect to shape survivors' quality of life (QoL). Furthermore, dominant models in disaster studies tend to rely on either clinical health measures or economic indicators, with limited integration of sociological frameworks that examine how structural inequalities mediate recovery (Ceyhan & Ceyhan, 2007; Abbott & Wallace, 2012). Few studies utilize multi-dimensional frameworks that link QoL to the broader social, legal, and institutional context in which survivors navigate their lives after disaster (van der Maesen & Walker, 2012; Beck et al., 2012).

The Social Quality (SQ) framework addresses key limitations in conventional well-being assessments by conceptualizing individual welfare across four interrelated dimensions: socio-economic security, social inclusion, social cohesion, and social empowerment (Walker & van der Maesen, 2004). While this model has found considerable application in comparative welfare and development research within the European Union and select non-Western settings (Berman & Philips, 2000; Pehle & Herrmann, 2013), its integration into disaster sociology—especially in contexts of humanitarian emergencies and forced displacement—remains limited and underexplored.

In the Turkish context, studies on the psychosocial consequences of earthquakes have tended to emphasize trauma or demographic correlates of PTSD (Bıçakcı & Okumuş, 2023; Yelboğa, 2023), while refugee research has largely focused on integration, social cohesion, and legal precarity (Uğuz, 2023; Sağıroğlu et al., 2023). Rarely have these strands been bridged to examine how refugees and host populations jointly experience post-disaster environments—especially in informal settlements and under conditions of legal vulnerability.

This article addresses these lacunae by integrating the social quality framework with a mixed-methods, cross-sectional household survey conducted among both Turkish nationals and Syrians under temporary protection in the most severely affected provinces of the February 2023 earthquakes: Adana, Adıyaman, Hatay, and Kahramanmaraş. The study offers three key contributions to the academic literature:

o **Conceptual Integration:** By applying the social quality framework in a post-disaster, refugee-inclusive context, the article offers a more holistic model of QoL that moves beyond psychological or economic metrics, capturing informational, legal, and protection-related dimensions of deprivation.

o **Empirical Novelty:** The data disaggregated by nationality, gender, and provincial location enables a fine-grained analysis of how different populations experience post-disaster vulnerabilities, particularly within informal settlement contexts largely neglected by national-level surveys or humanitarian coordination mechanisms.

o **Policy Relevance:** The study identifies gaps not only in basic services but also in informational access, perceived safety, and mental well-being, highlighting how QoL must be understood as an interdependent and intersectional outcome. These findings speak to broader concerns in disaster recovery about the invisibility of non-material forms of deprivation.

In sum, this article contributes to disaster sociology by empirically demonstrating the need for refugee-sensitive, protection-centered, and sociologically-informed approaches to post-disaster quality of life. It urges a shift from recovery paradigms that emphasize infrastructure and health metrics alone, toward frameworks that center human dignity, psychosocial well-being, and social inclusion as core components of resilience.

2. Research Strands

This research aimed to provide a comprehensive assessment of the living conditions and vulnerabilities of individuals residing in earthquake-impacted areas. The design of the study was informed by the project's log frame for analyzing the situation of populations affected by the Kahramanmaraş-centered recent earthquake(s) in the region as well as needs assessments undertaken by other humanitarian agencies specific to the situation of the survivors of the earthquakes in Türkiye. As the key purpose of the study was to gather representative primary data to establish benchmarks, data collection focused on a quantitative household survey.

The survey instrument was developed in two distinct formats—one addressing the specific conditions of refugees and asylum seekers, and the other focused on host community members. The refugee-specific version examined issues related to protection, safety, and dignity; solicited perceptions of key challenges and potential solutions; gathered input on preferred information channels and feedback mechanisms; and assessed access to shelter, WASH, healthcare, food, and education services. After the data were cleaned, analyses were conducted with disaggregation by sex, location, and other relevant variables. For indicators involving more abstract or multidimensional constructs, composite measures were employed—further details of which are provided in the corresponding section of the report. The results were subsequently cross-validated using secondary data sources that reflect the broader context of both refugee and host populations in Türkiye.

During the field study, the households were selected by using systematic random selection method. Throughout the random walking on the street, following the completion of first interview, the surveyors counted the households and next fifth one was interviewed. However, if any new street appears before reaching to fifth household, the surveyors will turn to new street and the second one was completed at this street. By this way, it was assured that distribution of the selected households is uniform in each neighborhood.

Over a three-month post-seismic observation period, we conducted longitudinal monitoring of quality of life (QoL) metrics in a cohort comprising 208 individuals (191 host community [91,82%] and 17 Syrians under temporary protection [8,18%]), all aged over 18 years and residing in four earthquake-hit provinces (Adana, Adıyaman, Hatay and Kahramanmaraş).

The primary phase of data collection was conducted between April and May 2023. Enumerators utilized tablet-based devices connected to an online survey monitoring system, which facilitated real-time oversight and quality control of the data collection process. To ensure accuracy and provide field-level support, protection officers conducted a total of 52 spot checks throughout the data gathering period.

Once the problems were identified in the datasets, the statistical data cleaning process started. This process was used to assist in producing more reliable, consistent, and accurate results by using the data. The process of data cleaning was as follows:

The dataset and identified invalid data were checked by using the pre-determined data quality standards and key necessities. Principally, some validation rules were developed prior to field work and surveyors' mistake were avoided. The reasons behind the wrong data and any possible underlying mechanisms were explored and necessary actions were accordingly taken. The research encountered the following limitations:

- In Türkiye, Ministry of Interior Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency (AFAD) are the lead Government entity in charge of the overall emergency response and recovery effort, including the management of formal displacement sites and coordination of response across all temporary settlements. Recognizing that AFAD are the lead in managing the formal settlements, the study aims at exploring the gaps on accessing essential services and basic needs materials among the survivors currently residing in the informal settlements such as self-settled tent communities in urban peripheries or rural areas, and scattered smaller sites (some in tents, some in makeshift shelters, greenhouses and other structures) (TSS, 2023).
- The questions used for the general analysis of the situation of the earthquake-affected population in the targeted locations were taken from the impact assessment tool. The tool provided a wealth of information from which further analysis is possible than the one presented in this report; however, some answers to quite similar questions give rise to questions about respondent's fatigue, and the tool's multi-sectoral nature also meant that some aspects of deeper sectoral analysis were not possible.
- Disaggregating data by sex and education levels was often inhibited by the small sample size, as the questionnaire did not collect the sex of the respondent, but the sex of the head of households and only the answers from those cases where respondents were the heads of households could be used for sex-disaggregated analysis.

3. Results

The earthquake affected an extensive geographic region in Türkiye, with approximately 14 million individuals impacted, 54,000 fatalities, and 108,000 injuries (AFAD, 2023; Yelboğa, 2023). Registered residents in the affected provinces total 13.4 million—representing 15.73% of the national population—meaning roughly one in six Turkish citizens was directly impacted (Sağroğlu & Ünsal, 2023). The destruction of infrastructure, residential collapse, and

widespread human loss had a profound psychological toll on survivors. Exposure—both direct and indirect—to trauma (e.g., loss of loved ones, disrupted safety, unresolved grief) significantly elevated post-earthquake anxiety and psychological distress, impairing overall quality of life (Uğuz, 2023). Even those not directly affected reported heightened societal distress, a phenomenon well-documented in large-scale disasters (Bıçakçı, 2023; Nakajima, 2012). Empirical studies, including research following the 2011 Van earthquake, confirm that perceived quality of life is a key predictor of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Ceyhan & Ceyhan, 2007). The cumulative impact of acute trauma and chronic stress can erode resilience and precipitate various psychiatric conditions.

Common psychological symptoms post-disaster include fear, anxiety, persistent negative thinking, sadness, and disrupted sleep and eating patterns—all contributing to lower life satisfaction. Research in Türkiye has shown a negative correlation between earthquake-related trauma and overall life satisfaction (Ozdemir et al., 2015; Yelboğa, 2023).

Respondents were asked to name the three most pressing challenges their households and communities face. Hygiene emerged as the most frequently cited issue, followed by clean water, income-generating activities, and food. Notably, “soft” issues—such as stress, anguish, and access to education—were ranked alongside essential “hard” needs like water, food, and healthcare.

Gender-disaggregated data reveal that women more frequently reported concerns related to hygiene (55%), clean water (42%), income (40%), and food (35%). Both men and women identified high prices of essential goods as a top-five issue. Together, household income and the affordability of basic necessities remain key stressors for earthquake survivors.

3.1. Having Access to the Educational Activities

To assess access to available services, respondents with children aged 6–18 were asked about participation in formal educational activities, both in and outside of school. Over two-thirds (73.2%) reported that children were not attending any educational activities. This figure was significantly higher among refugee households in earthquake-affected areas, where non-attendance reached 89.93%, indicating a severe disruption in educational access, particularly for displaced populations.

3.2. Having Urgent Needs Addressed

Urgent needs were assessed using indicators related to water consumption, food intake, and shelter conditions. Regarding water, 63.46% of respondents reported consuming the recommended 2.5–3 liters per person per day either often (38.94%) or every day (24.52%) during the past week. However, 36.54% consumed this amount only seldom (30.77%) or never (5.77%).

When asked whether their households could currently meet clean and safe drinking water needs, 86.54% said not at all (13.46%) or only partially (57.21%), while just 29.33% reported full access—highlighting a disconnect between actual consumption and perceived adequacy.

In terms of food, only 22.73% of respondents were satisfied with the quantity they consumed, while 25.91% expressed dissatisfaction. Shelter conditions also raised concern: 61.06% reported dissatisfaction—31.73% dissatisfied and 29.33% very dissatisfied. Only 37.02% were satisfied overall, with 33.65% satisfied and 3.37% very satisfied. These findings indicate significant service

gaps in critical areas—education, water, food, and shelter—underscoring the continued vulnerability of earthquake survivors.

3.3. Livelihoods and Income

Livelihoods and income emerged as one of the most critical challenges faced by earthquake-affected populations in Türkiye, ranking third among reported priority problems (56% of respondents), following hygiene and clean water. Related concerns—such as food insecurity, rising prices, limited employment, and inadequate health services—were also frequently mentioned.

Key livelihood challenges included inability to meet basic needs, poverty, job loss, and a lack of local employment opportunities. Based on an average household size of 4.9, reported household expenditures equate to approximately 260 TL per person monthly—well below the poverty (33,015 TL) and hunger (10,135.50 TL) thresholds reported by *Türk-İş* for a family of four.

While most households had at least one working member, 42.87% reported total monthly income between 0–5,000 TL. Only 16.55% earned between 5,001–10,000 TL, while the remainder earned 10,001 TL or more. In Adana, 60.71% of households reported incomes at or below 5,000 TL, with 17.86% earning 5,001–10,000 TL, and 21.43% above 10,001 TL. A similar income pattern was observed in Hatay, where 53.06% fell in the lowest income bracket. Livelihood concerns were particularly pronounced in Hatay and Adıyaman, indicating significant spatial variation in economic vulnerability across affected provinces.

3.4. Nutrition

In this survey, food emerged as the fourth most cited priority issue, mentioned by 35% of female and 16% of male respondents. Among those facing obstacles accessing food, the most frequently reported issue was high food prices (24% of women, 10% of men), followed by insufficient income. Other cited problems included hunger, limited food distributions, and market shortages.

Dietary data revealed that dairy and meat were the least consumed items: only 27% of respondents ate dairy, and 29% ate meat in the previous 24 hours. Field observations suggest this is due to both high prices and the absence of adequate refrigeration. In contrast, staple foods—bread, rice, noodles, cereals—were consumed by 70%, followed by legumes, eggs, nuts, and seeds (44%), and fruits and vegetables (35%).

Regarding food quantity satisfaction, only 22.73% of respondents were satisfied, while 25.91% were dissatisfied. A majority (51.36%) stated food quantity "could be improved." Dissatisfaction was notably high in Adana, where large-scale food distributions are lacking. Interestingly, even in Adıyaman, Hatay, and Kahramanmaraş—where aid delivery is more prevalent—many still expressed the need for improvement, indicating gaps in coverage or adequacy.

3.5. Sanitation

Access to clean, safe drinking water was generally adequate for a majority of respondents: 64.55% reported that their households could consistently meet water needs, while 35.45% indicated only partial access—an unexpectedly high proportion. When asked about actual consumption (2.5–3 liters per person daily over the past week), 60.91% reported sufficient intake always or often, whereas 39.09% consumed adequately only seldom or never. Overall, 46.14% expressed satisfaction with both access and quantity, while 53.86% desired improvements, suggesting that while minimum needs may be met, expectations for adequacy remain unmet.

Provincial data revealed disparities. In Adıyaman, access was generally sufficient, but in Hatay and Kahramanmaraş, partial access was significantly more common. In Hatay, those reporting partial access outnumbered those with full access more than fourfold; in Kahramanmaraş, the ratio was threefold. Similarly, in Adana, Hatay, and Kahramanmaraş, many respondents reported inadequate water consumption in the past week, despite an overall 63.46% who reported always or often consuming sufficiently. Regarding WASH, 33.18% of respondents had access to private toilet facilities during the last week, while 13.64% reported unsafe or non-private access. These findings highlight persistent gaps in safe and dignified sanitation access, despite relative improvements in water availability.

3.6. Shelter

Satisfaction with living conditions and quality of life was assessed via questions on shelter, sanitation, water, food, and healthcare access, alongside safety and protection. Overall, only 33.11% of respondents reported being satisfied or very satisfied, while 39.07% felt conditions "could be improved," and 27.82% expressed dissatisfaction.

Notably, dissatisfaction was highest regarding bath facility quality (39.55%), toilet quality (36.82%), and current shelter (31.82%). Conversely, the highest satisfaction rates were reported for shelter (38.63%), drinking water quantity (35%), and toilet quality (30.91%). Satisfaction with bathing facilities (26.36%) and food quantity (25.91%) remained low.

A considerable portion of respondents selected "could be better" across indicators, particularly for food quantity (over 50%) and drinking water (37.73%). Regarding shelter specifically, dissatisfaction outweighed satisfaction: 26.44% were dissatisfied or very dissatisfied, while only 19.23% reported satisfaction. In provincial breakdowns, similar trends persisted—for example, 20.19% of respondents in one province were dissatisfied, compared to just 2.4% who were satisfied with their shelter.

3.7. Mental Wellbeing

Mental health among earthquake-affected individuals was assessed using questions on fear, hopelessness, anger, overall happiness (0–10 scale), and sleep quality. Respondents could opt out if uncomfortable. Notably, distress, anguish, and stress—though not the most cited problems—ranked 7th among current priorities, following hygiene, clean water, income, and food, signaling the salience of mental health concerns.

Across the mental health indicators, 93.15% reported experiencing intense emotional distress—fear, hopelessness, or anger—either every day (26.95%) or often (3–4 days/week; 66.20%) in the week preceding the survey. Even among those who reported such feelings "seldom" (1–2 days), prevalence was notable. Specifically, 35.45% felt hopeless daily or often, and 26.82% reported uncontrollable anger. Fear was slightly less prevalent at 18.60%. Meanwhile, 61.05% reported anger and 57.70% hopelessness only seldom or not at all. Additionally, 6.81% declined to answer, potentially reflecting discomfort and suggesting underreporting.

Emotional distress patterns were similar across items, with hopelessness marginally more common than anger and fear. Overall, 15.06% experienced daily or frequent distress across all three indicators. Sleep hygiene was also impacted: while 48.69% experienced sleep disruptions seldom or not at all,

45.91% reported sleep problems every day or often, indicating significant disturbance in rest patterns post-disaster.

3.8. Safety and Protection

The perceived safety of earthquake-affected survivors was assessed through five questions on violence, nighttime safety, child safety, institutional protection, and reporting confidence. Less than half (40.90%) felt safe in daily life, walking alone at night, or allowing children to play outside always or most of the time, while 55.75% reported feeling safe only sometimes or not at all. Disaggregated responses show respondents felt relatively safer in daily life than walking at night, though only 30.45% felt their area was safe for children.

Although safety did not emerge as a top-priority concern overall, individual question responses revealed significant insecurity: 55.45% felt unsafe walking alone at night, 45.91% did not feel safe from daily violence, and nearly two-thirds perceived their neighborhoods as unsafe for children. This suggests a broader, underlying sense of insecurity.

Provincial breakdown reveals regional disparities. In Hatay, concerns were highest—respondents there were twice as likely to feel unsafe in daily life compared to those who felt safe. In contrast, perceptions in Kahramanmaraş were evenly split (22.28% for both safe and unsafe), while respondents in Adiyaman generally felt safer.

Regarding institutional protection, 50.91% lacked confidence that authorities could protect them from violence always or most of the time, and 42.27% felt this was only sometimes or not at all. Similarly, 58.18% lacked consistent confidence to report violence, mirroring the overall trend of mistrust in protective institutions—especially notable in Hatay, where distrust was more prevalent.

When asked which groups would struggle most to recover, 38.99% cited children (including orphans), followed by an “other” category (26.69%)—mainly referring to the elderly and those who lost family members. Farmers and residents with destroyed homes followed, then women (including pregnant women, 11.01%) and people with physical disabilities (10.09%).

3.9. Dignity

Regarding dignity-related perceptions, respondents were nearly evenly split on whether they felt respected, had their opinions valued, and contributed meaningfully to their communities, though over half affirmed these experiences consistently (54.09% for respect, 50.91% for valued opinions, 43.18% for community contribution). Disaggregated by location, negative perceptions were slightly more prevalent in Hatay and Adana compared to Adiyaman and Kahramanmaraş.

Knowledge of rights, obligations, and entitlements was assessed via six questions, addressing specific issues (livelihood, legal, mental health), violence reporting, subjective awareness, and adequacy of service information. Results revealed generally low awareness: 66.81% lacked knowledge on where to seek help for key issues; only 33.18% knew where to turn. While 58.18% knew how to report violence, 39.09% did not. Awareness of rights was also limited—55.91% reported none, while only 8.64% had strong awareness. Information on available services was largely insufficient: 62.27% felt uninformed, and just 7.73% considered information sufficient.

Livelihood support emerged as the most pressing information gap (45%),

followed by access to essential aid (30.91%). These priorities were confirmed by responses on preferred areas for information from authorities: 47.27% cited livelihoods, and 28.18% aid access.

Preferences for receiving and giving information varied by location and gender. In Adıyaman, Hatay, and Kahramanmaraş, face-to-face communication—especially via community leaders and agency staff—was dominant. In Adana, digital channels were favored. Gender-wise, both men and women preferred face-to-face interaction, followed by electronic means and printed IEC materials. Among women, 46.89% preferred face-to-face, 13.88% electronic, and 2.39% printed materials. Among men, 16.75% preferred face-to-face and 6.70% electronic means.

Conclusion

This study offers a sociologically grounded, empirically rich examination of post-disaster quality of life (QoL) in the aftermath of the 2023 Kahramanmaraş-centered earthquakes in Türkiye. By applying the social quality framework to both host and refugee populations, the findings challenge the prevailing recovery paradigms that prioritize material infrastructure and basic service provision, while often neglecting the experiential and relational dimensions of recovery—such as perceived safety, informational access, psychosocial well-being, and legal inclusion.

The results demonstrate that recovery is not solely a function of physical reconstruction but is deeply conditioned by structural inequalities, legal status, and localized trust in institutions. Notably, vulnerabilities were most acute in informal settlements and among groups already marginalized—women, elderly individuals, and Syrian refugees under temporary protection. This highlights the need to reconceptualize recovery not as a return to pre-disaster conditions, but as a political and social process shaped by intersecting axes of inequality.

Theoretically, the study extends the application of the social quality approach into disaster sociology and humanitarian response. While QoL has traditionally been assessed through health or economic indicators, our findings underscore its multidimensional character—incorporating subjective feelings of dignity and inclusion, relational dynamics of trust and cohesion, and systemic barriers to protection and rights realization. In doing so, the study demonstrates how disaster-induced deprivation is both material and symbolic, producing a layered experience of exclusion that conventional metrics often fail to capture.

Moreover, the data reveal a striking gap between formal humanitarian service availability and survivors' awareness and ability to access them. This disconnect suggests that informational inequality functions as a structural constraint on recovery—exacerbating the already unequal distribution of protection, aid, and psychosocial support. As such, the findings call for a reorientation of post-disaster policy frameworks to integrate rights-based communication strategies and localized, community-embedded psychosocial services.

In short, this study contributes to the growing literature advocating for intersectional and justice-oriented approaches to disaster recovery. It calls for a shift away from narrow metrics of physical survival toward comprehensive models of social recovery, where dignity, participation, and empowerment are not secondary but central to the reconstruction process. The social quality framework, as applied here, offers a viable analytic and policy tool for advancing this broader vision.

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